

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPATIAL PLANNING SYSTEM IN BULGARIA UNDER THE ACTIVE INFLUENCE OF TOURISM

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It is not by chance, and for quite some time now, that tourism has been referred to as a multiplier of the economy. Each job vacancy created in the sector stimulates the emergence of another 1,5 related jobs, generally contributing to the development of territories and settlements. In 2025, tourism revenues accounted for 10% of global GDP, providing employment for 330 million people, including representatives of so-called vulnerable groups: women (54% of those employed in tourism) and youth (50%, respectively) [15].

In 2025, the world recorded 1,52 billion tourists (60 million more than in 2024), generating revenues of USD 2,2 trillion. Europe remains the world's most successful tourist region, attracting 50% of all travelers (Table 1).

Table 1

Geographical distribution of tourists by world regions, 2025 [15]

Region	Number of tourists, <i>million people</i>	Change to the level 2024, %
Europa	793	+4
Asia – Pacific Ocean	~400	+10
America	220	+5
Africa	80	+7
Near East Region	~100	+12

In 2025, the theme of World Tourism Day, proclaimed by UNWTO, was “Tourism and Sustainable Transformation.” In this way, global public attention was focused on the green transformation of tourism, manifested in particular in the spread of environmentally responsible solar hotels, the emergence of plastic-free beaches, etc. In 2026, the focus will shift to “Digital Agenda and Artificial Intelligence to Redesign Tourism”: virtual tours, AI-based recommendations, and blockchain technologies to ensure booking security. Notably, AI already plans up to 30% of tours: from personalized routes to mass tourist flows.

Against the backdrop of progressive changes in the global tourism industry, Bulgaria demonstrates steady progress, striving to mitigate seasonal fluctuations in resort occupancy. Final data for 2025 indicate an average increase of 6% in the number of tourists in Bulgaria

[14]. In the capital, tourist flows increased by 10% in January–September 2025 compared to 2024; the number of overnight stays also rose. The largest numbers of visitors came from Italy, Greece, Israel, and Turkey [13]. Interestingly, domestic tourism in Bulgaria has also intensified [5].

The direct determinant factors behind these positive changes include:

- Bulgaria's accession to the Schengen Area (from January 1, 2025), which made the country more accessible for short trips by Europeans;

- Expansion of air connections. The main airports in the country are Sofia Airport (SOF) – the country's main hub; Burgas Airport (BOJ), serving the southern coast; Varna Airport (VAR), serving the northeastern part of the country; Plovdiv Airport (PDV), used mainly for charter flights, including in winter; and Gorna Oryahovitsa Airport. Airlines Wizz Air, Ryanair, and Bulgaria Air have expanded the number of flights and routes to increase Bulgaria's accessibility and international tourist flows [14];

- Reduction of seasonality and segmentation of the tourism sector. A clear seasonal segmentation of tourism has been established in the country. The 2025 ski season became the strongest compared to previous years, as the number of overnight stays increased by almost 24% [3]. In 2025, the flow of vacationers from Romania increased by 9% (almost 1 million overnight stays) [5]. According to forecasts, Bulgaria is expected to continue experiencing growth in tourist flows in 2026 in the active, ecological, cultural, and wellness tourism segments [13].

Positive changes in the country's political and socio-geographical position directly affect its spatial planning system. In the context of a course toward balanced sustainable development consistent with European trends, the distribution of Bulgaria's territory (110,996,76 km²) has the following balance: urbanized areas – 4,8%; transport areas – 2,8%; agricultural land – 54,5%; forests – 33,3%; areas occupied by water bodies – 1,9%; protected areas – 2,1%; disturbed land – 0,4%; other – 0,3% [5]. The geographical distribution of land use in the country is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Land use in Bulgaria as of 31.12.2024 [5]

According to the statistical accounting system adopted in Europe (NUTS), Bulgaria distinguishes six regions at NUTS level 1 (Fig. 2) and 28 regions at NUTS level 2 (Fig. 2). The country's natural population decline and growing regional development disparities stimulate the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works to conduct thematic studies and review options for future changes to the country's NUTS 2 map up to 2027 (Fig. 3). Elements of the lowest level for statistical purposes include 264 municipalities (LAU 1) and 5,302 settlements (LAU 2) in Bulgaria. Elements of the Tercet typology in Bulgaria include applied cluster types as a basis for the degree of urbanization (DEGURBA) and urban–rural typologies; local and regional typologies; and other typologies covering border areas, riverine regions (the Danube River), and mountain regions.

With an urbanization level of 76%, the country has only one metropolis – the city of Sofia (1,3 million people in 2024), which is not only the capital and economic center of the country but also a functional urbanized zone, a transport hub, and the center of an agglomeration of the same name. Sofia is a member of the Network of European Metropolitan Regions and Areas [2]. Spatial and strategic development of the Sofia metropolis is overseen by the municipal enterprise Sofiaplan, whose implemented projects include: the Long-Term Development Strategy of the Municipality of Sofia until 2050; the current Master Urban Plan of Sofia and its future update; the Integrated Municipal Development Plan for 2021–2027; and plans, strategies, and policies for the sustainable development of the Sofia municipality [2].

Fig. 2. Visualization of NUTS levels in Bulgaria [7]

Fig. 3. Visualization of the transformation of NUTS levels in Bulgaria up to 2027 [1]

The capital agglomeration includes 7 municipalities at the LAU 1 level and 146 individual settlements (LAU 2), with a total area of almost 3,550 km² (3.2% of the country's territory). In 2021, the Gross Regional Product (GRP) of the Sofia agglomeration accounted for 43% of the national economy, and GRP per capita was twice the national average. A significant number of industrial facilities in manufacturing, transport, and logistics are located in neighboring municipalities that are part of the capital agglomeration. However, the distribution of foreign direct investment in Bulgaria is extremely uneven: about 97% of its volume is concentrated in the municipality of Sofia, ensuring high economic activity of the local population and, accordingly, a low unemployment rate compared to other parts of the country.

The second-largest city in the country is Plovdiv (636 thousand people in 2024). It has a lower population concentration, relatively smaller investment in development, and high tourist attractiveness, as confirmed by the number of overnight stays (Table 2).

**Table 2
Comparative characteristics of the largest cities in Bulgaria as of the end of 2024 [5]**

City	Population (<i>thousands</i>)	Functional role	Industrial specialization	Transport and logistics	Tourism (<i>overnight stays</i>)
Sofia	1 296	Capital, administrative center	IT, finance, construction, trade	Airport, railway, highways	2 267 902
Plovdiv	636	Cultural capital	Mechanical engineering, food, textile industries	Major railway hub, highway, airport	1 414 851

Varna	438	Maritime capital, port city	Shipbuilding, tourism, services, trade	Seaport	4 752 786
Burgas	195	Industrial port city	Oil refining, chemical industry, logistics, tourism	Seaport, railway	9 905 089
Ruse	186	Danube port, border city	Mechanical engineering, transport, chemical industry	River port (bridge across the Danube to Romania)	173 093

An analysis of the websites of the cities of Sofia and Plovdiv [9, 12] shows a typical structure and content: general information, historical background, a tourist page, local documentation, a “hotline” platform, and sections on healthcare, transport, budget, education, reporting on adopted decisions, etc. Neither of Bulgaria’s two largest cities has a brand book; nor do they have adaptive website formats for people with visual impairments. Both websites are available in Bulgarian and English (the English versions are more limited).

The website of the city of Sofia [9] is inaccessible to owners of IP addresses from Ukraine (the analysis was conducted from Germany). Mobile viewing functionality is also limited. Event marketing of Sofia at the national level is represented by the Sofia International Film Festival and Loop Live Festival. The main challenges facing the capital lie in the environmental sphere: significant air pollution and poor air quality monitoring; high car dependency (private vehicles); irrational construction and reduction of green areas; and urban overpopulation.

The website of the city of Plovdiv [12] is accessible to all visitors and is also bilingual. Plovdiv fully presents its status as the cultural capital of the country through: Plovdiv – European Capital of Culture 2019; International Fair Plovdiv; International Chamber Music Festival (Plovdiv); and International Folklore Festival. As in Sofia, significant levels of air pollution are recorded in Plovdiv, especially in winter (due to private households); social problems persist in the Roma district of Stolipinovo; and there is lagging development of transport infrastructure (lack of cycling networks and outdated public transport).

Overall, Bulgaria’s two largest cities are developing in the same direction, facing similar development problems while simultaneously possessing significant potential. A major improvement would be greater informational openness of the websites of Sofia and Plovdiv—and subsequently of other Bulgarian cities—for residents and visitors, improved functionality, and the development of city brand books. However, the significant gap between the country’s two largest cities only confirms Bulgaria’s monocentric status and the divergence of its spatial development.

In the context of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, Bulgaria monitors a number of indicators reflected in statistics, implementing relevant programs on the one hand and simultaneously working on competitiveness in the European tourism services market on the other. Goal 11 – to make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and

sustainable – is reflected on the national statistical portal through indicators such as the rate of severe housing deprivation by poverty status; disaster impacts; government expenditures by function; municipal waste recycling rates, etc. [5]. Notably, as early as 2011, the National Statistical Institute included regular reporting of official information on indicators measuring progress in implementing the goals and reforms outlined in the National Reform Program of the Republic of Bulgaria.

The subjects of spatial planning in the country include the Ministry of Spatial Development and Public Works; the Directorate for National Construction Control; and the Directorate for Territorial Organization and Administrative-Territorial Structure. Bulgaria implemented a long-term National Concept for Spatial Development for 2013–2025 [6]; the medium-term “Regional Development” Program for 2021–2027 [11]; and other program documents [4, 10].

Post-socialist Bulgaria is confidently implementing its own development vector, with the tourism sector serving as a significant catalyst for this progress, as evidenced by statistics. Having become an EU member in 2017, the country introduced NUTS standards and is working to adjust them in line with ongoing social changes. Despite unstable governance in Bulgaria (seven parliamentary elections over the past five years, with a predominance of democratic and pro-European forces alongside pro-Russian parties that are also nationalist), a number of program documents aimed at spatial harmonization and achieving the Sustainable Development Goals have been adopted. Digitalization tools can significantly strengthen the potential of LAU-level territories, while further consideration of the specifics of Tercet typology elements will help mitigate spatial divergence and reduce seasonality in tourism. The decentralization strategy is expected to enhance the potential of the entire network of Bulgarian cities.

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